

THERMAL EVOLUTION OF THE MOON DOMINATED BY THE EARTH Wenhao Zhao¹, Harriet Lau¹ and Stephen Parman¹, ¹ Department of Earth, Environmental and Planetary Sciences, Brown University, Providence, RI 02912, USA, (wenhao_zhao@brown.edu).

Introduction: Observations from the Apollo and Chang'E missions suggest that the Moon may have retained its internal heat for a longer period than previously thought. At least three major thermal puzzles remain debated: (1) Remanent magnetism suggests that the Moon sustained an active dynamo until at least ~ 2.0 Ga. (2) Radiometric dating of Ferroan Anorthosites (FANs) indicates that the Lunar Magma Ocean (LMO) remained molten for approximately ~ 200 million years after its formation. (3) The heat source driving young lunar volcanism, such as that observed in the Chang'E-5 samples, remains unclear. Radiogenic heating from KREEP-rich (Potassium, Rare Earth Elements and Phosphorus) components has largely been ruled out. These findings suggest that different regions or components throughout the evolution of the Moon may have retained heat for longer, implying the possible existence of a persistent and so far overlooked internal heat source.

Tidal dissipation comes from the conversion of orbital and rotational energy into internal heat within a planetary body, caused by periodic deformation under the gravitational influence of another object. Although tidal heating has been proposed as a potential energy source for the Moon, it has historically been overlooked. However, recent studies have renewed interest in this mechanism. Notably, Nimmo et al. (2024) proposed that tidal dissipation associated with the Moon's passage through the Laplace resonance could account for the prolonged solidification timescales of the LMO. This hypothesis suggests that tidal heating may have played a more significant role in the Moon's early thermal evolution.

Here, we propose that the Moon could have been reheated through tidal dissipation—even in the absence of a Laplace resonance. This hypothesis is supported by the following observations and reasoning: (1) At certain Earth–Moon semi-major axis (a), tidal dissipation within the Moon is enhanced due to its rheological behavior. When the Moon's internal temperature cooled to a critical value range (T_{cri}) of a melt fraction of approximately 40%, tidal dissipation would have approached its maximum efficiency (Zahnle et al., 2015). (2) Since the Moon was much closer to Earth during its early evolution, the rate of Earth–Moon orbital evolution may have been primarily controlled by tidal dissipation within the Earth. Geological evidence—such as the formation of komatiites—suggests that Earth's mantle underwent major thermal transitions between ~ 3.0 and 2.0 Ga, cooling toward its own T_{cri} . This transition may

have significantly altered tidal dissipation rates and, by extension, the thermal histories of both Earth and Moon.

Method: In this study, we develop a parameterized thermal evolution model for the Moon that emphasizes the role of viscous tidal dissipation. The model simulates heat transport through the lunar mantle and incorporates the influence of Earth's thermal state transition around ~ 3.0 Ga to calculate the evolution of the Earth–Moon semi-major axis. Key components of the model include:

(1) Parameterized Mantle Heat Flux – The model imposes a time-dependent mantle heat flux driven by either convection or conduction.

(2) Viscosity-Dependent Tidal Dissipation – The viscosity of the lunar mantle is computed as a function of temperature and melt fraction, which governs the efficiency of tidal dissipation for the lunar mantle.

(3) Earth-Driven Evolution of a – The model incorporates variations in Earth's mantle melt fraction to estimate Earth's Love number (k_2) and quality factor (Q), which in turn affect the tidal evolution of the Earth–Moon distance.

Result: Our model generated a tidal heating rate on the order of $\sim 10^{11}$ watts, comparable to the radiogenic heat production of the whole lunar mantle. This enhanced tidal dissipation persisted from $\sim 10^4$ to 10^6 years following the Moon's formation and extended until around 3.0 Ga, coinciding with key transitions in the Earth. Residual tidal heating continues at a lower level until approximately 1.0 Ga.

The model provides a unifying framework to explain several long-standing observations from lunar samples, including the formation of FANs at ~ 4.36 Ga, the rapid decline of lunar magmatism around 3.0 Ga, and the occurrence of late-stage volcanism. By coupling Earth's internal thermal evolution to the tidal response of the Moon, the study identifies a previously underappreciated mechanism for delayed internal heating on the Moon.

More broadly, the model has implications for planetary magnetism, lunar asymmetry, and the orbital evolution of the Earth–Moon system. Although simplified, it captures a fundamental aspect of planetary thermal evolution: the transition from a fully molten state to a partially molten, and eventually solid, interior. This transitional phase is marked by a peak in tidal dissipation, offering a plausible and significant way to make the Moon hot again after its formation.